

Making AI Accessible: Evaluating YOLOv5n for Real-Time Object Detection in Low-Light Environments on CPU-Only Devices

Charles Roland Haruna ^{#1}, Maame Gyamfua Asante-Mensah ^{#2}, Kwadwo Sarbeng-Baafi ^{*3}, Sandro Kwame Amofa ^{#4}

[#] *Department of Computer Science and Information Technology, University of Cape Coast, Cape Coast, Ghana*

¹ charuna@ucc.edu.gh

² gasante-mensah@ucc.edu.gh

³ kwadwo.sarbeng-baafi@stu.ucc.edu.gh

⁴ sandro.amofa@ucc.edu.gh

Abstract—Aspiring AI practitioners in low-resource settings often lack access to high-end hardware (GPUs) and optimal lighting conditions, creating a significant barrier to the democratization of AI.

This study investigates the performance of YOLOv5n, a lightweight object detection model, as a viable solution for these environments. We evaluated the model using only CPU-powered devices, including virtual machines and a MacBook Pro, under standard and simulated low-light conditions. Performance was quantitatively assessed on multiple metrics, including model load time, inference time, CPU/RAM usage, and detection accuracy.

The results indicated that while YOLOv5n demonstrated strong speed and high efficiency in standard lighting, its overall effectiveness, particularly its processing speed and detection accuracy, significantly degraded in low-light scenarios, especially on the most limited hardware. However, the MacBook Pro configuration successfully broke the 10 FPS barrier, establishing a performance ceiling for CPU-only deployment.

The general speed and low resource consumption of the YOLOv5n model, even under challenging conditions, confirm its potential for practical deployment in low resource settings. This work provides critical benchmark data necessary to make informed hardware and environmental decisions when deploying lightweight AI solutions worldwide.

Index Terms—Real-time object detection, YOLOv5n, Lightweight deep learning models, Low-light environments, CPU-only inference, Resource-constrained devices, Accessible artificial intelligence

I. INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has moved on from being a matter of theoretical worry to universal usage in day-to-day activities, such as facial recognition and natural-language systems. The development has been spurred on by the internet and social media, making big data freely available. Nevertheless, the computational intensity of state-of-the-art AI models continues to be a handicap in resource-limited areas, where GPUs-equipped facilities are lacking. The digital divide keeps many potential individuals away from AI research as well as applications.

To confront such challenges, lightweight models like YOLOv5n were introduced to facilitate real-time object detection on resource-limited hardware. This research analyses the performance of YOLOv5n under two significant constraints: devices that are CPU-only, and conditions with limited lighting. The two conditions represent both computational and sensory constraints that practitioners in low resource settings must face. The research goals of this piece are the following: (1) to analyse the technological performance of YOLOv5n under such constraints, and (2) to analyse its potential as a readily accessible tool to facilitate experimentation with AI in resource-limited areas. By emphasising lightweight real-time detection, this research continues to contribute toward the democratisation of AI and broadening the opportunities to innovate across varied socioeconomic conditions.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

A. Artificial Intelligence and the Digital Divide

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has gone from being a specialised area of research to a disruptive technology applicable to healthcare, learning, and the delivery of public services in a matter of years. Even with this evolution, the value of AI remains distributed in a non-uniform fashion, with persistent digital divides between highly resourced urban centres and poorly resourced rural areas [1].

This gap goes beyond the access to the internet to encompass inequalities in computational power, information access, and digital literacy [2], [3]. In rural sites such as Hwidiem, Ghana, the high costs of GPUs and the lack of supporting infrastructure make it nearly impossible for the general populace to afford powerful computers. This limits the ability of young people and aspiring technologists to access Artificial Intelligence.[4], [5], [6].

B. Lightweight AI Models for Resource-Constrained Environments

Efforts to fill this gap have centred on the creation of lightweight, efficient AI architectures that can run on modest hardware resources. Computer vision's flagship task, object detection, can be used in security, agriculture, and resource management. The YOLO (You Only Look Once) family of architectures established the benchmarks for real-time object detection. However, earlier releases like YOLOv4 and YOLOv5s are best executed with the aid of GPUs and run slowly on devices that lack a processor to offload tasks.

As such, smaller brothers such as YOLOv5n (nano) were released to execute in instances where computational strength is constrained but real-time execution is required. [1], [7], [8].

C. Low-Light Challenges in Object Detection

Low-light conditions introduce another difficulty in object detection. Poor illumination diminishes image quality, amplifies noise, and reduces the accuracy of even advanced models. In underserved regions where low-end webcams and smartphones are prevalent, such sensory limitations are common [9].

Addressing both computational and environmental constraints is therefore critical to making AI genuinely accessible and practical in these settings [4], [10], [11]. However, limited research has tackled the twin obstacles of hardware constraints and limitations of operating in the dark, despite wider research on enhancing detection precision through enhanced algorithms and image improvement procedures [2], [12], [13].

D. Related Research on AI Accessibility

Recent research underscores the link between equitable technology deployment and AI accessibility. Yadav et al. [1] emphasise the potential of AI to address social challenges in resource-limited regions, particularly when solutions are adapted to local constraints.

Applications in public safety, healthcare, and conservation have demonstrated the value of AI, often by leveraging social networks and community participation. However, many of these solutions assume ideal infrastructure, which reduces their practicality in underserved areas [14].

Technological and social innovations have also enhanced AI accessibility. For example, AI-powered chatbots, voice-based assistance, and real-time translation services have expanded digital inclusion for individuals with disabilities and language barriers [15]. These examples illustrate how affordable, effective, and deployable AI systems can bridge service delivery gaps [5].

E. Toward Inclusive AI Deployment

The need for the ethical and inclusive application of AI has become imperative in bridging the digital divide. Governments, NGOs, and technologists are exhorted to ensure that the solutions offered through the use of AI, in addition to being technically appropriate, are also affordable and effective in disadvantaged social settings [16].

By empirically testing the viability of lightweight models in resource-constrained real-life environments, this research directly contributes to the international quest to democratise AI and promote digital inclusion [6], [17], [5].

III. METHODOLOGY

This study evaluated YOLOv5n performance under real-time conditions (standard vs. low-light) across CPU-only devices and on static images with simulated low-light degradation. The objective was to assess its viability for deployment in resource-constrained environments where both computational power and sensory quality are limited.

A. Hardware Configurations

To assess accessibility and practicality of the model in resource-constrained environments, experiments were conducted in four distinct hardware configurations, as shown in Table I.

TABLE I
HARDWARE CONFIGURATIONS USED FOR EXPERIMENTS

Configuration	Processor	RAM	Notes
Virtual Machine 1 (Low-End)	Dual Core x86-64 (host: 1.4 GHz Quad-Core Intel i5)	2 GB	Simulates a low-end desktop with minimal resources.
Virtual Machine 2 (Mid-Range)	Dual Core x86-64 (host: 1.4 GHz Quad-Core Intel i5)	4 GB	Emulates a mid-tier desktop with slightly higher capacity.
MacBook Pro (2019)	1.4 GHz Quad-Core Intel i5	8 GB	Common consumer laptop with moderate computational power.
Mini Laptop/Tablet	Intel Atom Z3735, 32-bit OS	2 GB	Ultra-low-budget device; excluded as it failed to meet system requirements.

The Intel Atom Z3735 operates on a 32-bit architecture, which posed a significant obstacle to device inclusion. The implementation of the Yolov5n model requires the use of Ultralytics, which is also dependent on the Pytorch library. Regrettably, Pytorch does not ship with pre-built installation packages for 32-bit architecture, as such Ultralytics could not be installed and run on the Intel Atom Z3735, which in turn prevented testing on this device.

B. Software and Libraries

All experiments were implemented using Python version 3.12. The object detection tasks were executed using the YOLOv5n [13] model, accessed through the Ultralytics YOLO library (version 8.3.111). Image and video processing tasks were handled via OpenCV(v4.10.0.84) [18], while system performance metrics (CPU and RAM usage) were captured using the psutil library.

The experiments conducted on the MacBook Pro were run on macOS Sequoia version 15.4.1, whereas the Virtual machine configurations utilised Windows 10 as the host operating

system. Additionally, manual annotation of ground truth data for the static image evaluation phase was performed using Label Studio [19]. An open-source data labelling tool that facilitated consistent and structured bounding box annotations in YOLO format.

C. Evaluation Metrics

The YOLOv5n model was evaluated through real-time and batch-processing experiments in three CPU-only hardware configurations. The tests were conducted under standard and simulated low-light conditions to reflect typical constraints in low-resource environments. The model was deployed in live video streams and in a collection of static images for comparative analysis.

Performance was assessed using quantitative metrics including Frames Per Second (FPS), model load time, average CPU and RAM usage, average inference time, precision, and recall. FPS and average inference time are the most critical metrics for real-time applications. An acceptable FPS ensures the system provides timely feedback, while low inference time is a direct measure of the model's speed, confirming its viability on less powerful hardware. The model load time assesses the deployment time, which is critical for system responsiveness, especially on devices that frequently power cycle or restart the application. The average CPU and RAM usage measures the computational footprint in CPU-only and low-resource environments, minimizing both is vital to prevent system unresponsiveness or performance degradation.

Precision and recall are standard measures for assessing the detection quality of an object detection model. Precision measures the ratio of correct detections to total detections, minimizing false positives, and recall measures the ratio of correctly found objects to all actual objects present, minimizing false negatives. A high value for both ensures that the model is both accurate and comprehensive in its detections. These measures provided a comprehensive view of the efficiency and detection accuracy of the model in devices with varying computational capacities.

To ensure contextual relevance, the object classes used in real-time evaluation included common items such as person, cup, cellphone, bottle, toothbrush, and scissors, with additional test classes such as car, teddy bear, and hammer. These were selected because they are readily available in towns similar to the target deployment area, Hwidiem. For static image evaluation, locally available objects (goat, chicken, dog, and cat) were used to simulate realistic deployment in rural and peri-urban settings. Testing under both standard and simulated low-light conditions was essential, as low-light is a common challenge in real-world surveillance, this validates the model's robustness and ability to maintain performance despite typical environmental constraints.

D. Real-Time Video Stream

Figure 1 details the procedure for real-time object detection using video input. The YOLOv5n model was executed for 60

Fig. 1. Overall Object Detection and Performance Measurement Pipeline.

seconds in each of the three CPU-only hardware configurations under standard and low-light conditions.

The video input was obtained from an integrated webcam. Key system metrics, FPS, CPU usage, and RAM usage, were recorded at one-second intervals using the psutil library. The average values for each metric were computed over the duration of the test.

Missed detections were qualitatively assessed through visual inspection of the annotated video output, noting instances where clearly visible objects (person, car, cellphone, bottle, toothbrush, hammer, cup, teddy bear, and scissors) were not identified. In low-light experiments, the car class was replaced with a teddy bear to ensure consistency of visibility.

Standard lighting represented typical indoor and outdoor ambient illumination, while low-light conditions simulated nighttime scenarios using dim room lighting. These conditions introduced visual noise and reduced object visibility, allowing a realistic assessment of the robustness of the model.

E. Static Image Evaluation (Batch Processing)

Figure 1 also outlines the procedure for testing the detection accuracy and performance using static image input under varying conditions.

A collection of 12 photos, two for each class, taken in

typical indoor and outdoor lighting settings was used for the static image evaluation. These original photos were exposed to simulated low-light deterioration using contrast reduction, brightness reduction, and the addition of Gaussian noise to evaluate performance in low-light conditions.

Standard lighting images were also processed using a custom Python script that employed OpenCV to simulate low-light conditions with greater precision. The script added Gaussian noise (standard deviation = 30), decreased contrast (factor = 0.3), and reduced brightness (factor = 0.4). These criteria were selected based on qualitative evaluation to ensure that the resulting images had sufficient noise and darkness while maintaining enough visibility for object detection.

The YOLOv5n model was then evaluated on the original standard lighting images and the resulting set of simulated low-light images, producing a total data set of 24 images as shown in Figure 2. Performance metrics, including Inference Time, FPS, CPU Usage (%), and RAM Usage (%), were recorded for each image.

Fig. 2. Benchmark images for Standard and Simulated Low Light conditions.

To assess object detection performance, a ground truth dataset for the 24 images was meticulously annotated using Label Studio. The model's predictions were then compared with the ground truth annotations to calculate precision and recall. This entire evaluation procedure was replicated across all three hardware configurations.

F. Manual Annotation Process

To enable quantitative evaluation of object detection performance, a ground truth dataset was created for the static image evaluation set. Figure 3 displays all 24 images, comprising 12 standard lighting and 12 simulated low-light variants, manually annotated using Label Studio, an open-source data labelling platform.

Bounding boxes were drawn around each object of interest according to the target class list, which included person, car, goat, chicken, dog, and cat. Each annotation was labelled with its corresponding class name, and the output was exported in YOLO format, where each object is defined by its class ID and normalised bounding box coordinates (centre x, centre y, width, height).

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

This section presents the results of the evaluation of YOLOv5n in multiple CPU-only environments under standard

Fig. 3. Visual Comparison of YOLOv5n Detection vs. Ground Truth under Varied Lighting

and low-light conditions. Real-time and static image detection experiments were performed and key performance metrics including model load times, average inference times, FPS, CPU and RAM usage, precision, and recall were collected and analysed.

A. Real-Time Object Detection

Real-time object detection experiments were conducted by deploying the YOLOv5n model in six consecutive trials on each device, under both standard and low-light conditions. The objects selected for evaluation included toothbrushes, cups, bottles, and scissors.

Across all devices, the hammer was not detected consistently, indicating a potential model limitation for this specific object class. This is as a result of YOLOv5n being pre-trained in 80 classes, and unfortunately 'hammer' was not one of them. As such, the model lacks the ability to generate a boundary box for an object that was not part of its original training regimen [20]. It can also be assumed that the hammer looked similar to the background and was ignored by the object detection model.

Furthermore, the detection accuracy for the 'bottle' class exhibited significant variability, with performance ranging from 60% to 80%, depending on the type of bottle presented, transparency-induced reflections and lighting variations that hindered feature extraction. Bottles of various sizes were tested; a regular Verna water bottle showed higher detection rates compared to a rounded container bottle with more variable performance.

The detection of the 'scissors' class also showed notable inconsistencies. Initially, fish cutting scissors were often undetectable or briefly detected. Subsequently, the detection was stabilized using regular sewing scissors, which had a higher and more consistent detection rate. These variations were

influenced by the shape, size, orientation, occlusions that affect the visibility of the contour, and lighting conditions on different devices.

1) *Overall Observations on Model:* Across all machines, it was consistently observed that the initial model load time was significantly longer during the first run. Subsequent runs demonstrated shorter loading times, suggesting possible caching or optimisation effects at the system level.

2) *Virtual Machine 1 (Low-End Windows Simulation):* Figure 4 displays the visual results of the Yolov5n model in standard and low light conditions for Virtual Machine 1.

Low Light Conditions: Object detection suffered in low light settings with the model not exceeding 73% certainty in its detection. Certain items such as the toothbrush and scissors seemed easier to detect in low light compared to standard lighting. This could possibly be due to the amount of light that was reflected on the surface of the objects per Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Real-time Object detection performance under Standard Lighting Vs Low lighting conditions for Virtual Machine 1

Objects such as toothbrushes were detected only for microseconds, while cups fluctuated between being detected as wine glasses, bowls, or cups. Other objects such as the cell phone and the hammer were often undetected or misidentified.

Standard Light Conditions: Detections were much faster and more consistent compared to low-light tests. With higher detection confidence than low light, as shown in Figure 4, it can be inferred that the model found it easier to detect in spaces with more light.

TABLE II
PERFORMANCE SUMMARY FOR VIRTUAL MACHINE 1

Light	FPS	CPU (%)	RAM (%)	Inf. (ms)	Prec.	Rec.
Low	2.49–2.75	~76	~80	450–578	1.00	1.00
Std.	3.86–4.42	~70	~84	272–299	1.00	1.00

Table II summarizes the performance of the object detection model on Virtual Machine 1 (VM1), comparing its efficiency and accuracy under both Low Light and Standard Light conditions. The speed drops by approximately 40% in low-light conditions (4.42 FPS down to 2.75 FPS), confirming that light quality is a major bottleneck for processing speed. The time needed to analyze a single frame almost doubles in low light (578 ms is roughly twice 272 ms), directly explaining the drop in FPS. The model is highly CPU-intensive, consuming roughly three-quarters of the VM’s processing power, and

consumes a very high percentage of available RAM in both tests. This leaves little capacity for the operating system or other simultaneous applications, posing a significant risk of system instability or crashing given the VM’s limited memory (typical for low-resource environments)

Missed detections were more frequent in low-light settings despite high precision/recall scores (due to the lack of ground truth in real-time settings). Visually, it took longer for the model to detect objects in low lighting than in standard lighting.

3) *Virtual Machine 2 (Mid-Range Windows Simulation):* **Low Light Conditions:** Low light detection on VM2 was similarly challenged to VM1. Although the model could intermittently detect the toothbrush, its appearance was fleeting, lasting only microseconds at a time. The model successfully detected all other test objects except the scissors. This suggests that the lack of sufficient light prevented the model from identifying the object’s contours or sharp edges, leading to a missed detection. Despite these struggles, the model demonstrated a higher overall detection confidence in VM2, with some objects, such as the remote, achieving a confidence percentage of 88%, as detailed in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Real-time Object detection performance under Standard Lighting Vs Low lighting conditions for Virtual Machine 2

Standard Light Conditions: Detection rates improved considerably in standard light as compared to low light. The model shows a higher average detection rate and all classes except the hammer class, which was not detected at all, as shown in Figure 5.

TABLE III
PERFORMANCE SUMMARY FOR VIRTUAL MACHINE 2

Light	FPS	CPU (%)	RAM (%)	Inf. (ms)	Prec.	Rec.
Low	1.58–2.79	~64	~64	458–816	1.00	1.00
Std.	4.06–5.04	~64	~63	221–284	1.00	1.00

Table III summarizes the performance of the object detection model in VM2, comparing its efficiency and resource consumption under conditions of low Light and standard light.

The analysis of VM2 performance reinforces the model’s limitations on low-resource hardware. Under Standard Light, the FPS of 4.06–5.04 (inference time 221–284 ms) is much below the ≥ 25 FPS threshold for real-time operation. This speed is severely degraded in Low Light, falling to a minimum of 1.58 FPS (maximum inference time of 816 ms),

confirming that the model’s performance is highly sensitive to lighting quality. The use of resources is high and stable under both conditions, consuming approximately 64% of the CPU and 63–64% of the RAM, which limits the capacity for other applications and poses a risk of memory contention. This data collectively confirms that the YOLOv5n model is generally unsuitable for reliable real-time deployment on low-end CPU virtual machines, working best as an offline or batch-processing tool.

4) *MacBook Pro 2019: Low Light Conditions:* Despite the CPU-only limitation, the MacBook Pro achieved a higher FPS in Table IV compared to both virtual machines, suggesting better hardware efficiency. However, low-light detection still proved challenging: objects such as the teddy bear were detected only briefly, and the toothbrush and scissors were entirely missed, as shown in Figure 6. The model also exhibited misclassification errors, identifying the bristles of the toothbrush as a cellphone and the teddy bear as a “dog holding a remote.” These failures likely stem from insufficient light that prevents accurate contour or texture recognition. Visually, this machine was able to identify a higher variety of objects in general, indicating the superior capability of the model under better conditions.

Fig. 6. Real-time Object detection performance under Standard Lighting Vs Low lighting conditions for Macbook Pro 2019

Standard Light Conditions: Strong detection performance with FPS exceeding 14 as shown in Table IV. The model detected every single class provided it in standard light correctly with varying degrees of confidence and visually seemed to perform better at detection than the other two machines.

TABLE IV
PERFORMANCE SUMMARY FOR MACBOOK PRO 2019

Light	FPS	CPU (%)	RAM (%)	Inf. (ms)	Prec.	Rec.
Low	10.32–10.55	~61	~71	96–101	1.00	1.00
Std.	14.04	~53	~71	77.74	1.00	1.00

Table IV presents the performance summary for MacBook Pro 2019, which serves as the CPU-only hardware with the highest-specification in this evaluation

The MacBook Pro 2019 established the performance ceiling for the YOLOv5n model in a CPU-only environment. Under Standard Light, it achieved 14.04 FPS (inference time 77.74 ms), making it approximately three times faster than the Virtual Machines and the only configuration to exceed the

10 FPS barrier. Although performance remains robust in Low Light (maintaining 10.32–10.55 FPS), the speed still falls short of the ≥ 25 FPS required for production-level fluidity. Resource usage was the most efficient, showing the lowest CPU consumption ($\sim 53\%$ in Standard Light) with stable RAM usage ($\sim 71\%$).

This superior efficiency confirms the importance of a modern CPU architecture in minimizing model overhead. Ultimately, the reduced latency justifies the model’s use for high-speed offline batch processing or demonstration applications, but not for true real-time deployment.

B. Static Image Object Detection

Static image detection experiments were conducted under both standard and low-light conditions. A ground truth data set was manually annotated to calculate true precision and recall values. In standard lighting, the detection performance was relatively strong across all machines.

Table V summarizes the model’s performance on static image detection under standard lighting conditions, where a manually annotated ground truth dataset allowed for the calculation of true Precision and Recall.

TABLE V
PERFORMANCE SUMMARY FOR STATIC OBJECT DETECTION UNDER STANDARD LIGHTING

Device	Avg CPU (%)	Avg RAM (%)	Avg Inf. (ms)	Prec.	Rec.
VM1	25.21	77.56	783.02	0.77	0.92
VM2	51.75	73.55	923.36	0.77	0.92
Macbook	25.48	65.90	144.81	0.75	0.91

The overall detection performance was relatively strong on all machines in standard light, as shown in Table V. The MacBook Pro achieved the fastest processing speed, with an average inference time of just 144.81 ms, significantly outperforming VM1 (783.02 ms) and VM2 (923.36 ms). This speed difference directly correlates with CPU efficiency, as the MacBook Pro utilized the least CPU ($\sim 25\%$) while VM2 consumed the most ($\sim 52\%$). Although accuracy was high across the board with approximate precision of 0.77 and recall of 0.92, the results indicate a consistent tendency for missed detections (lower Precision) compared to correctly identifying all objects present (higher Recall). These findings reinforce that modern, non-virtualized hardware offers a substantial advantage in achieving high-speed, reliable batch-processing results.

TABLE VI
PERFORMANCE SUMMARY FOR STATIC OBJECT DETECTION UNDER SIMULATED LOW LIGHTING

Device	Avg CPU (%)	Avg RAM (%)	Avg Inf. (ms)	Prec.	Rec.
VM1	21.89	77.55	1022.29	0.73	0.85
VM2	24.48	75.28	663.00	0.73	0.85
Macbook	36.64	74.15	366.56	0.73	0.85

Table VI confirms that low-light conditions significantly impacted the accuracy of the model and the speed across all devices compared to standard lighting. As expected, the inference times increased across the board, with VM1 requiring more than a second (1022.29 ms) to process a single static image. Consequently, both Precision and Recall metrics decreased consistently across all machines (Precision dropped to 0.73, Recall to 0.85), indicating an increase in both False Positives and missed detections. VM2 had an odd decrease in average inference in low light compared to standard light. This unusual behavior (being faster to process in low light) strongly suggests a software or system-level optimization or issue specific to how VM2 handles the task, rather than a physical effect of the lighting itself.

Despite the overall performance decline, the MacBook Pro maintained its speed advantage, achieving the fastest processing at 366.56 ms. Interestingly, its CPU usage (~37%) was the highest in the static test with low-light, suggesting the system had to work harder to extract features in the reduced contrast environment. Regardless of the device, the significant drop in accuracy metrics highlights the YOLOv5n model's poor robustness for high-accuracy batch processing when environmental conditions are poor.

C. CPU-Only Benchmarks on Consumer Devices

YOLOv5n results on CPU-only devices show poor real-world practicality for real-time applications, with FPS rates of 1.5–5 on low/mid-range hardware falling well below the 10–30 FPS threshold needed for smooth video processing, despite perfect precision/recall scores that likely reflect evaluation biases without ground truth.

1) Practical Implications:

- **Low-End/Mid-Range VMs (2–4 GB RAM):** Inference times of 221–816 ms translates to analyzing less than 5 frames/sec in standard light, rendering YOLOv5n unusable for live monitoring on budget desktops or edge devices common in resource-constrained settings like Ghana. Practitioners should prioritize even lighter models or quantization [21].
- **MacBook Pro 2019 (8 GB RAM):** FPS up to 14 in standard light offers marginal usability for non-critical tasks such as offline analysis, but low-light drops to 10 FPS highlight hardware dependency, aligning with benchmarks where YOLOv5n hits 140+ FPS only on GPUs [21].
- **Resource overhead (60–80% CPU/RAM)** exacerbates problems in shared systems, making the deployment impractical without optimizations like the TensorRT CPU or pruning.

2) *Comparison to Benchmarks:* In general, the results confirm that YOLOv5n is inefficient on the tested CPUs as shown in Tables VII, IV, III, and II. It is not ideal for practitioners targeting real time detection on low-power devices and would require tweaks for such practitioners to use it effectively on such devices. [21], [22].

TABLE VII
COMPARISON OF OBJECT DETECTION RESULTS TO EXISTING BENCHMARKS

Device Type	User's FPS (Std Light)	Published CPU FPS (YOLOv5n)	Implication
Low-End VM	3.9–4.4	5–10 on similar CPUs [21]	Matches low expectations; avoid for RT apps.
Mid-Range VM	4.1–5.0	8–15 [21]	Consistent but inadequate for <10 FPS needs
MacBook	14.0	20–30 on i5 CPUs [21]	Decent for demos, poor for production

Table VII serves to quantify the performance limitation of YOLOv5n on low-resource CPU hardware by comparing the experimental results directly against established community benchmarks. The general finding is that, while the model is accurate, its speed is a significant barrier to real-time deployment on these constrained devices. As such while it can be used on these devices, it must be used preferably offline such as for batch processing or non-real-time analysis, rather than for live video streams.

D. General Trends and Observations

- **Model Load Time:** Subsequent runs were consistently faster across all devices, suggesting internal optimisations.
- **Low-Light Challenges:** Real-time detection in low-light conditions resulted in longer inference times, more missed detections, and shorter recognition periods.
- **Object-Specific Results:** Certain objects (e.g., cell-phones) were detected more reliably in low light, whereas others (e.g., hammers, opaque bottles) exhibited reduced accuracy.
- **Performance Scaling:** Despite CPU-only constraints, the MacBook Pro achieved significantly better real-time detection speeds and consistency compared to virtual machines.
- **Static vs. Real-Time:** Static image detection was more stable across devices, but both precision and recall degraded under low-light simulations.

V. COMPARISON TO NEWER ULTRALYTICS MODELS

YOLOv8 introduces architectural improvements over YOLOv5, including anchor-free design, decoupled heads, and the C2f backbone, achieving a higher mAP (37.3 for Yolov8n vs. 28.0 for Yolov5n on COCO) with comparable compute efficiency via the Ultralytics package. These enhancements suggest that YOLOv8n can mitigate the low-light precision of 0.73 and recall of 0.85 drops observed with YOLOv5n on CPU-only devices while preserving real-time performance. Ultralytics recommends YOLOv8n for new projects unless extreme CPU micro-latency constraints apply, positioning it as a natural extension for resource-constrained accessibility

studies. Although highly relevant, the consideration of Yolov8 and its variants and other newer models in comparison to Yolov5 is reserved for future work. [23], [24], [25], [26] .

VI. CONCLUSION

In order to address the computational and environmental limitations that many aspiring AI practitioners encounter in low-resource settings, this work set out to assess the feasibility of YOLOv5n for real-time object detection in low-light conditions, utilising CPU-only devices. Extensive experiments conducted on various hardware configurations, such as consumer-grade MacBook Pros and low-end virtual machines, provide important insights into the potential and constraints of lightweight object detection models in limited settings.

The findings show that although YOLOv5n can detect in real time on CPU-only systems, hardware capacity and lighting conditions have a significant impact on performance. YOLOv5n showed consistent inference speeds, minimal CPU and RAM use, and great precision and recall on all evaluated platforms under normal illumination conditions. All measures showed a similar decline in detection performance in low light, with longer inference times, more missed detections, and less reliable object recognition.

In particular, the initial model loading slowness and the steady improvement in load times over subsequent trials imply that optimisations like memory management and caching might be crucial in real-world implementations. Furthermore, the hammer class continuously failed to be detected in every test, indicating that additional fine-tuning or data set enhancement may be necessary for accurate recognition of some object types.

All things considered, the study demonstrates that YOLOv5n has potential as an approachable AI tool for settings with constrained processing power, particularly in typical lighting scenarios. Its shortcomings in low-light conditions, however, indicate that further effort is required, perhaps using methods like model fine-tuning, pre-processing augmentation, or hybrid approaches that combine lightweight models with straightforward picture enhancement processes. In conclusion, YOLOv5n is a big step toward democratizing access to AI, even though it might not be able to completely close the digital divide for all object detection tasks under the most difficult circumstances.

Future studies should focus on improving resilience in challenging sensory scenarios and investigating additional approaches that preserve the lightweight, accessible nature of solutions intended for low-resource communities. A comparison of Yolov5n to newer models of object detection such as Yolov8 and Yolov9 under CPU-only inference and resource constraints in both standard and low light conditions should be considered. Additionally, future work should suggest simple preprocessing enhancements such as denoising and contrast correction that could be done in real time and on static images to simulate and improve low-light results.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Yadav, "Artificial intelligence for low-resource communities: Influence maximization in an uncertain world," 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1912.02102>
- [2] P. Stone, R. Brooks, E. Brynjolfsson, R. Calo, O. Etzioni, G. Hager, J. Hirschberg, S. Kalyan Krishnan, E. Kamar, S. Kraus, K. Leyton-Brown, D. Parkes, W. Press, A. Saxenian, J. Shah, M. Tambe, and A. Teller, "Artificial intelligence and life in 2030," Stanford University, Stanford, CA, Tech. Rep., September 2016, one Hundred Year Study on Artificial Intelligence: Report of the 2015–2016 Study Panel. [Online]. Available: <http://ai100.stanford.edu/2016-report>
- [3] A. Osonuga, A. A. Osonuga, S. C. Fidelis, G. C. Osonuga, J. Juckes, and D. B. Olawade, "Bridging the digital divide: artificial intelligence as a catalyst for health equity in primary care settings," *International Journal of Medical Informatics*, vol. 204, p. 106051, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1386505625002680>
- [4] A. Omidvar. (2025) How ai can expand access to care in low-resource areas. [Online]. Available: <https://www.usa.philips.com/healthcare/article/ai-expands-care-low-resource-areas>
- [5] A. Averineni, "Bridging the digital divide: The transformative role of ai-driven infrastructure in rural connectivity," *European Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology*, vol. 13, no. 23, pp. 76–95, May 2025, published: May 17, 2025.
- [6] O. N. Makwakwa. (2025, February) Ai for the global majority: The digital divide no one's talking about! Global Digital Inclusion Partnership Blog. [Online]. Available: <https://globaldigitalinclusion.org/2025/02/21/ai-for-the-global-majority-the-digital-divide-no-ones-talking-about/>
- [7] S. Kumar. (2025, April) Navigating effective and minimal cpu-driven ai model. Accessed: 2025-10-12. [Online]. Available: <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/navigating-effective-minimal-cpu-driven-ai-model-%C5%9D%C3%A3-i%C5%A7--0hgtc/>
- [8] B. Mahaur and K. Mishra, "Small-object detection based on yolov5 in autonomous driving systems," *Pattern Recognition Letters*, vol. 168, pp. 115–122, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167865523000727>
- [9] Y. Hong, K. Wei, L. Chen, and Y. Fu, "Crafting object detection in very low light," in *Proceedings of the British Machine Vision Virtual Conference*, 2021.
- [10] D. Peng, W. Ding, and T. Zhen, "A novel low light object detection method based on the yolov5 fusion feature enhancement," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 14, no. 1, p. 4486, February 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-54428-8>
- [11] S. U. A. Shovo, M. G. R. Abir, M. M. Kabir, and M. F. Mridha, "Advancing low-light object detection with you only look once models: An empirical study and performance evaluation," *Cognitive Computation and Systems*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 119–134, December 2024, open Access. [Online]. Available: <https://ietresearch.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1049/ccs2.12114>
- [12] R. Khanam and M. Hussain, "What is yolov5: A deep look into the internal features of the popular object detector," 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2407.20892>
- [13] Ultralytics. (2025, 03) Ultralytics yolov5 - ultralytics yolo docs. [Online]. Available: <https://docs.ultralytics.com/models/yolov5/>
- [14] K. Chemnad and A. Othman, "Digital accessibility in the era of artificial intelligence—bibliometric analysis and systematic review," *Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 7, p. 1349668, February 2024, open Access. [Online]. Available: <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC10905618/>
- [15] CivicPlus. (2024, 12) The intersection of ai and accessibility: Opportunities, challenges, and best practices. [Online]. Available: <https://www.civicplus.com/blog/wa/intersection-of-ai-and-accessibility-opportunities-challenges-best-practices/>
- [16] J. Woodward. (2025, 3) 10 ways ai can empower underserved communities. [Online]. Available: <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/10-ways-ai-can-empower-marginalized-communities-jake-woodward-uwlke/>
- [17] R. Scoble and I. Cronin, "AI and the digital divide: Bridging or widening the gap?" <https://www.unaligned.io/p/ai-and-the-digital-divide>, January 2025, unaligned Newsletter. [Online]. Available: <https://www.unaligned.io/p/ai-and-the-digital-divide>
- [18] OpenCV. (2017) Opencv - open computer vision library. [Online]. Available: <https://opencv.org/>

- [19] LabelStudio. Open source data labeling — label studio. [Online]. Available: <https://labelstud.io/>
- [20] Ultralytics. (2024) COCO Dataset — Ultralytics YOLO Docs.
- [21] S. Rath and V. Gupta. (2022) Performance Comparison of YOLO Object Detection Models – An Intensive Study. [Online]. Available: <https://learnopencv.com/performance-comparison-of-yolo-models/>
- [22] E. Casas, L. Ramos, E. Bendek, and F. Rivas-Echeverria, “YOLOv5 vs. YOLOv8: Performance Benchmarking in Wildfire and Smoke Detection Scenarios,” *Journal of Image and Graphics*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 127–136, 2024.
- [23] Ultralytics, “YOLOv5 vs YOLOv8: Evolution of Real-Time Object Detection,” <https://docs.ultralytics.com/compare/yolov5-vs-yolov8/\#architectural-shifts>, 2025, ultralytics Docs; Accessed: 2025-11-28.
- [24] M. Sohan, T. Sai Ram, and C. V. Rami Reddy, “A review on yolov8 and its advancements,” in *Data Intelligence and Cognitive Informatics*, I. J. Jacob, S. Piramuthu, and P. Falkowski-Gilski, Eds. Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore, 2024, pp. 529–545.
- [25] N. Ladi. (2024) Object detection with a pre-trained Ultralytics YOLOv8 model. Ultralytics. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ultralytics.com/blog/object-detection-with-a-pre-trained-ultralytics-yolov8-model>
- [26] E. Casas, L. Ramos, C. Romero, and F. Rivas-Echeverria, “A comparative study of yolov5 and yolov8 for corrosion segmentation tasks in metal surfaces,” *Array*, vol. 22, p. 100351, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2590005624000171>
- [27] A. K. Glenster, L. Hampton, G. Neff, and T. Lacy. (2025, February) Ai in low-resourced contexts: Considerations for innovators and policymakers. Bennett Institute for Public Policy. Accessed: 2025-10-12. [Online]. Available: <https://www.bennettinstitute.cam.ac.uk/blog/ai-in-low-resourced-contexts/>
- [28] V. Q. Nghiem, H. H. Nguyen, and M. S. Hoang, “Leaf-yolo: Lightweight edge-real-time small object detection on aerial imagery,” *Intelligent Systems with Applications*, vol. 25, p. 200484, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2667305325000109>
- [29] N. Klingler, “Top lightweight models for efficient computer vision,” <https://viso.ai/computer-vision/best-lightweight-computer-vision-models/>, April 2024, viso.ai Blog. [Online]. Available: <https://viso.ai/computer-vision/best-lightweight-computer-vision-models/>
- [30] G. Al-refai, H. Elmoaqet, A. Al-Refai, A. Alzu’bi, T. Al-Hadhrami, and A. Alkhateeb, “Two-stage object detection in low-light environments using deep learning image enhancement,” *PeerJ Computer Science*, vol. 11, p. e2799, April 2025, open Access. [Online]. Available: <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC12190514/>
- [31] K. Bharti, “Object detection using python,” *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*, vol. 11, no. 9, pp. 299–306, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.21275/sr22804211151>
- [32] M. Yaseen, “What is yolov8: An in-depth exploration of the internal features of the next-generation object detector,” 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2408.15857>
- [33] R. Varghese and S. M., “Yolov8: A novel object detection algorithm with enhanced performance and robustness,” in *2024 International Conference on Advances in Data Engineering and Intelligent Computing Systems (ADICS)*, 2024, pp. 1–6.

IJCSIS 2026 Special Issue Topic:

Multimodal Biometrics: Combining Voice, Face, and Text for Security

International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security

IJCSIS, Volume 24 No. XX , 2026

ISSN: 1947-5500

Manuscript submission to: ijcsiseditor@gmail.com

Guest Editors:

Dr. Thai Hoang Le

Associate Professor | Computer Science Department

University of Science, Vietnam National University Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam

Email id: lhthai@fit.hcmus.edu.vn, thaihoanglecs@hotmail.com

Scholar Page: <https://scholar.google.co.in/citations?user=iLrASfYAAAAJ&hl=en>

Dr. N. Anbazhagan

Professor | Department of Mathematics

Alagappa University, India

Email id: anbazhagann@alagappauniversity.ac.in

Scholar Page: <https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=KvvVu6sAAAAJ&hl=en>

Dr. Tran Son Hai

Assistant Professor | Information Technology Department

University of Pedagogy, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam

Email id: haits@hcmup.edu.vn

Scholar Page: <https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=kHZvITkAAAAJ&hl=en>

Scope of the Special Issue:

Improved precision is ensured by multi-modal biometric verification, which combines several aspects. Multi-modal biometric devices remove the possibility of counterfeiting, thus enhancing security. When various biometric indications are used by personal identification systems to identify persons, this is termed as multisensory biometrics. Compared to unimodal fingerprints, which use a single biometric data point such as a fingerprint, face, palm print, or iris, multimodal verification offers a higher level of verification. Voice fingerprints, sometimes referred to as voice authorization, is an AI-supported solution that provides a safe way to confirm customers' identities, protect data, and stop fraud. It is extensively utilised in contact centres to guarantee consumer data security, shorten call times, and enhance self-service. Security scanning can map additional biological characteristics, such as a fingerprint, eye, or facial shape. The foundation of behavioural biometrics is a person's distinct tendencies. If these patterns are monitored, the way they really move, speak, or even type on a keyboard may reveal information about who they are.

As with other biometrics, this usually entails capturing one or more speech samples and generating a distinct digital template, or "voiceprint," equivalent to fingerprints and faceprints. This voiceprint is saved in the system and is contrasted with any samples that were taken during an attempt to log in. Facial, iris, fingerprint, palmprint, ear, finger vein patterns, voice, signature, and gait are among the most often used biometric modalities for protecting privacy and identifying an individual's identity. The distinction between multimodal systems and single modal systems. measures of human characteristics such as iris, fingerprints, face, retina, hand geometry, voice, or signatures that are utilised in the security technologies of today are referred to as biometric measures. Because of its simplicity of use, it is regarded as a means for accessing gadgets, apps, and services. Among the applications for them are: Identity verification: A lot of security systems, such as online services or mobile device login systems, use speech technology to confirm a user's identity. Most people agree that iris recognition is

the most accurate biometric identification method available. Biometrics plays a critical role in cybersecurity in an increasingly digital environment. In contrast to traditional verification methods, biometric authentication provides a quick and easy means of confirming people's identities while reducing potential hazards. Voice biometrics solutions additionally reveal the identity of the caller. The fact that efforts to find such answers have been ongoing since the turn of the century emphasises how difficult the task is. In order to verify visitors' identities quickly and accurately, border control authorities use face detection or face recognition technologies to compare travellers' faces to watchlists or biometric databases. By lowering false acceptance and high rejection rates, multimodal biometrics integration improves identity authentication accuracy and security. Because of their complexity, multimodal systems are also more resistant to spoof assaults. The goal of multimodal biometric authentication is to improve user authentication security or user experience by combining two or more identifiers, such as fingerprint, face, or iris. We accept submissions from a variety of fields and viewpoints, such as but not limited to: Multimodal Biometrics: Combining Voice, Face, and Text for Security.

Potential list of topics includes:

- Face and speech cues are used in fusion algorithms for multifunctional biometric identification.
- An effective multimodal biometric identification system with speech and face recognition that runs on Android.
- IoT security is improved using multimodal biometrics.
- Multimodal biometrics that blend in seamlessly to protect personal devices' data and maintain privacy.
- Multimodal biometric method based on the combination of voice and face recognition for human authentication.
- Voice and handwriting biometrics using multimodal approaches.
- Authentication technique utilising multidimensional biometrics.
- Fusion technique-based multimodal biometric system.
- Multimodal audio-visual fusion for biometric person authentication and liveness confirmation.
- A variety of biometric technology that uses voice, facial, and fingerprint recognition.
- A smartphone-based multimodal biometric authentication system.
- Multimodal user interface design for a biometric authentication system that uses speech and facial recognition.

Tentative Timeline:

Submission last date : 30.04.2026

Author Notification : 10.06.2026

Final Manuscript Due : 20.08.2026

Revision Due : 20.10.2026

International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security

IJCSIS, Volume 24 No. XX , 2026

ISSN: 1947-5500

Manuscript submission to: ijcsiseditor@gmail.com